

On Properties of Generalized Bi- Γ -Ideals of Γ -Semirings

Teerayut Chomchuen and Aiyared Iampan

Abstract—The notion of Γ -semirings was introduced by Murali Krishna Rao as a generalization of the notion of Γ -rings as well as of semirings. We have known that the notion of Γ -semirings is a generalization of the notion of semirings. In this paper, extending Kaushik, Moin and Khan's work, we generalize the notion of generalized bi- Γ -ideals of Γ -semirings and investigate some related properties of generalized bi- Γ -ideals.

Keywords— Γ -semiring, bi- Γ -ideal, generalized bi- Γ -ideal.

I. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES

THE notion of Γ -semirings was introduced and studied in 1995 by Murali Krishna Rao [10] as a generalization of the notion of Γ -rings as well as of semiring, and the notion of generalized bi-ideals was first introduced for rings in 1970 by Szász [12], [13] and then for semigroups by Lajos [8]. Many types of ideals on the algebraic structures were characterized by several authors such as: In 2000, Dutta and Sardar [3] studied the characterization of semiprime ideals and irreducible ideals of Γ -semirings. In 2004, Sardar and Dasgupta [11] introduced the notions of primitive Γ -semirings and primitive ideals of Γ -semirings. In 2008, Kaushik, Moin and Khan [7] introduced and studied bi- Γ -ideals in Γ -semirings, Pianskool, Sangwirojtanapat and Tipyota [9] introduced and studied valuation Γ -semirings and valuation Γ -ideals of a Γ -semiring, and Chinram [1] gave some properties of quasi-ideals in Γ -semirings. In 2009, Jagatap and Pawar [6] introduced the concept of minimal quasi-ideal in Γ -semirings. Some properties of minimal quasi-ideals in Γ -semirings are provided. In 2010, Ghosh and Samanta [5] studied the relation between the fuzzy left (respectively, right) ideals of Γ -semirings and that of operator semiring. In 2011, Dutta, Sardar and Goswami [4] introduced different types of operations on fuzzy ideals of Γ -semirings and proved subsequently that these operations give rise to different structures such as complete lattice, modular lattice on some restricted class of fuzzy ideals of Γ -semirings. In 2012, Bektaş, Bayrak and Ersoy [2] introduced and studied the characterization of soft Γ -semirings and soft sub- Γ -semiring.

The concept of ideals for many types of Γ -semirings is the really interested and important thing in Γ -semirings. Therefore, we will introduce and study generalized bi- Γ -ideals of Γ -semirings in the same way as of bi- Γ -ideals of Γ -semirings which was studied by Kaushik, Moin and Khan [7].

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To present the main results we first recall the definition of a Γ -semiring which is important here and discuss some elementary definitions that we use later.

Definition I.1. [10] Let M and Γ be two additive commutative semigroups. Then M is called a Γ -semiring if there exists a mapping $\cdot : M \times \Gamma \times M \rightarrow M$ (the image $\cdot(a, \alpha, b)$ to be denoted by $a\alpha b$ for all $a, b, c \in M$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$) satisfying the following conditions:

- (1) $a\alpha(b + c) = a\alpha b + a\alpha c$,
- (2) $(a + b)\alpha c = a\alpha c + b\alpha c$,
- (3) $a(\alpha + \beta)b = a\alpha b + a\beta b$,
- (4) $a\alpha(b\beta c) = (a\alpha b)\beta c$

for all $a, b, c \in M$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Let M be a Γ -semiring, A and B nonempty subsets of M , and Λ a nonempty subset of Γ . Then we define

$$A + B := \{a + b \mid a \in A \text{ and } b \in B\}$$

and

$$A\Lambda B := \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \lambda_i b_i \mid n \in \mathbb{Z}^+, a_i \in A, b_i \in B \text{ and } \lambda_i \in \Lambda \text{ for all } i \right\}.$$

If $A = \{a\}$, then we also write $\{a\} + B$ as $a + B$, and $\{a\}\Lambda B$ as $a\Lambda B$, and similarly if $B = \{b\}$ or $\Lambda = \{\lambda\}$.

Example I.2. [6] Let \mathbb{Q} be set of rational numbers. Let $(S, +)$ be the commutative semigroup of all 2×3 matrices over \mathbb{Q} and $(\Gamma, +)$ commutative semigroup of all 3×2 matrices over \mathbb{Q} . Define $W\alpha Y$ usual matrix product of W, α and Y for all $W, Y \in S$ and for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Then S is a Γ -semiring but not a semiring.

Example I.3. [6] Let \mathbb{N} be the set of natural numbers and $\Gamma = \{1, 2, 3\}$. Then (\mathbb{N}, \max) and (Γ, \max) are commutative semigroups. Define the mapping $\mathbb{N} \times \Gamma \times \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, by $a\alpha b = \min\{a, \alpha, b\}$ for all $a, b \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Then \mathbb{N} is a Γ -semiring.

Example I.4. [6] Let \mathbb{Q} be set of rational numbers and $\Gamma = \mathbb{N}$ the set of natural numbers. Then $(\mathbb{Q}, +)$ and $(\mathbb{N}, +)$ are commutative semigroups. Define the mapping $\mathbb{Q} \times \Gamma \times \mathbb{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}$, by $a\alpha b$ usual product of a, α, b ; for all $a, b \in \mathbb{Q}$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Then \mathbb{Q} is a Γ -semiring.

Example I.5. [2] For consider the additively abelian groups $\mathbb{Z}_8 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7\}$ and $\Gamma = \{2, 4, 6\}$. Let $\cdot : \mathbb{Z}_8 \times \Gamma \times \mathbb{Z}_8 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_8$, $(y, \alpha, s) = y\alpha s$. Then \mathbb{Z}_8 is a Γ -semiring.

Definition I.6. A nonempty subset A of a Γ -semiring M is called

- (1) a *sub- Γ -semiring* of M if $(A, +)$ is a subsemigroup of $(M, +)$ and $a\gamma b \in A$ for all $a, b \in A$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$.
- (2) a *Γ -ideal* of M if $(A, +)$ is a subsemigroup of $(M, +)$, and $x\gamma a \in A$ and $a\gamma x \in A$ for all $a \in A, x \in M$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$.
- (3) a *quasi- Γ -ideal* of M if A is a sub- Γ -semiring of M and $A\Gamma M \cap M\Gamma A \subseteq A$.
- (4) a *bi- Γ -ideal* of M if A is a sub- Γ -semiring of M and $A\Gamma M\Gamma A \subseteq A$.
- (5) a *generalized bi- Γ -ideal* of M if $A\Gamma M\Gamma A \subseteq A$.

Remark I.7. Let M be a Γ -semiring. We have the following:

- (1) Every quasi- Γ -ideal of M is a bi- Γ -ideal.
- (2) Every bi- Γ -ideal of M is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal.

Definition I.8. A Γ -semiring M is called a *GB-simple Γ -semiring* if M is the unique generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M .

II. MAIN RESULTS

Before the characterizations of generalized bi- Γ -ideals of Γ -semirings for the main results, we give some auxiliary results which are necessary in what follows. By Lemma I.7 (2) and [7], we have the following lemma.

Lemma II.1. Let M be a Γ -semiring and $a \in M$. Then $a\Gamma M$ and $M\Gamma a$ are generalized bi- Γ -ideals of M .

Lemma II.2. Let M be a Γ -semiring and $\{B_i \mid i \in I\}$ a nonempty family of generalized bi- Γ -ideals of M with $\bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \neq \emptyset$. Then $\bigcap_{i \in I} B_i$ is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M .

Proof: For all $i \in I$, we have

$$\left(\bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \right) \Gamma M \Gamma \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \right) \subseteq B_i \Gamma M \Gamma B_i \subseteq B_i.$$

Thus

$$\left(\bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \right) \Gamma M \Gamma \left(\bigcap_{i \in I} B_i \right) \subseteq \bigcap_{i \in I} B_i.$$

Hence $\bigcap_{i \in I} B_i$ is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M . ■

Lemma II.3. Let M be a Γ -semiring and $\emptyset \neq A \subseteq M$. Then

$$A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A \quad (1)$$

is the smallest generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M containing A .

Proof: Let $B = A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A$. Then $A \subseteq B$. Therefore

$$\begin{aligned} & B\Gamma M\Gamma B \\ &= (A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A)\Gamma M\Gamma (A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A) \\ &\subseteq [A(\Gamma M\Gamma)(A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A)] \cup \\ &\quad [A\Gamma M\Gamma A(\Gamma M\Gamma)(A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A)] \\ &\subseteq [A(\Gamma M\Gamma)A \cup A(\Gamma M\Gamma)A\Gamma M\Gamma A] \cup \\ &\quad [A\Gamma M\Gamma A(\Gamma M\Gamma)A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A(\Gamma M\Gamma)A\Gamma M\Gamma A] \\ &\subseteq [A\Gamma M\Gamma A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A] \cup [A\Gamma M\Gamma A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A] \\ &= A\Gamma M\Gamma A \\ &\subseteq A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A \\ &= B. \end{aligned}$$

Thus $B = A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A$ is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M . We shall show that B is the smallest generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M containing A . Let C be a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M containing A . Then

$$A\Gamma M\Gamma A \subseteq C\Gamma M\Gamma C \subseteq C.$$

Thus

$$B = A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A \subseteq C.$$

Hence B is the smallest generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M containing A . ■

By Lemma II.3, let (A) be the smallest generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M containing A . Therefore

$$(A) = A \cup A\Gamma M\Gamma A. \quad (2)$$

It is also very common to denote the smallest generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M containing $\{a\}$ as (a) .

Lemma II.4. Let T be a sub- Γ -semiring of a Γ -semiring M , $a \in M$ and $(a\Gamma T\Gamma a) \cap T \neq \emptyset$. Then $(a\Gamma T\Gamma a) \cap T$ is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of T .

Proof: Consider

$$\begin{aligned} & (a\Gamma T\Gamma a \cap T)\Gamma T\Gamma (a\Gamma T\Gamma a \cap T) \\ &\subseteq [(a\Gamma T\Gamma a)\Gamma T \cap T\Gamma T]\Gamma (a\Gamma T\Gamma a \cap T) \\ &\subseteq [(a\Gamma T\Gamma a)\Gamma T \cap T]\Gamma (a\Gamma T\Gamma a \cap T) \\ &\subseteq [[(a\Gamma T\Gamma a)\Gamma T]\Gamma (a\Gamma T\Gamma a)] \cap [T\Gamma (a\Gamma T\Gamma a \cap T)] \\ &\subseteq [(a\Gamma T\Gamma a) \cap (T\Gamma a\Gamma T\Gamma a)] \cap T \\ &\subseteq (a\Gamma T\Gamma a) \cap T. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(a\Gamma T\Gamma a) \cap T$ is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of T . ■

Lemma II.5. Let M be a Γ -semiring and $a \in M$. Then $a\Gamma M\Gamma a$ is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M .

Proof: Consider

$$(a\Gamma M\Gamma a)\Gamma M\Gamma (a\Gamma M\Gamma a) = a\Gamma (M\Gamma a\Gamma M\Gamma a\Gamma M)\Gamma a \subseteq a\Gamma M\Gamma a$$

Hence $a\Gamma M\Gamma a$ is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M . ■

Proposition II.6. Let M be a Γ -semiring and T a sub- Γ -semiring of M . Then every subset of T containing $M\Gamma T$ is a sub- Γ -semiring of M .

Proof: Let A be a subset of T such that $M\Gamma T \subseteq A$. Then

$$A\Gamma A \subseteq M\Gamma T \subseteq A.$$

Hence A is a sub- Γ -semiring of M . ■

Proposition II.7. *Let M be a Γ -semiring and T a Γ -ideal of M . Then every subset of T containing $M\Gamma T \cup T\Gamma M$ is a Γ -ideal of M .*

Proof: Let B be a subset of T such that $M\Gamma T \cup T\Gamma M \subseteq B$. Then

$$M\Gamma B \subseteq M\Gamma T \subseteq M\Gamma T \cup T\Gamma M \subseteq B$$

and

$$B\Gamma M \subseteq T\Gamma M \subseteq T\Gamma M \cup M\Gamma T \subseteq B.$$

Hence B is a Γ -ideal of M . ■

Proposition II.8. *Let M be a Γ -semiring and T a quasi- Γ -ideal of M . Then every subset of T containing $T\Gamma M \cap M\Gamma T$ is a quasi- Γ -ideal of M .*

Proof: Let C be a subset of T such that $T\Gamma M \cap M\Gamma T \subseteq C$. Then

$$C\Gamma C \subseteq T\Gamma M \cap M\Gamma T \subseteq C$$

and

$$C\Gamma M \cap M\Gamma C \subseteq T\Gamma M \cap M\Gamma T \subseteq C.$$

Hence C is a quasi- Γ -ideal of M . ■

Proposition II.9. *Let M be a Γ -semiring and T a bi- Γ -ideal of M . Then every subset of T containing $T\Gamma M\Gamma T$ and all of its images is a bi- Γ -ideal of M .*

Proof: Let D be a subset of T such that $T\Gamma M\Gamma T \subseteq D$ and $D\Gamma D \subseteq D$. Then

$$D\Gamma M\Gamma D \subseteq T\Gamma M\Gamma T \subseteq D.$$

Hence D is a bi- Γ -ideal of M . ■

Proposition II.10. *Let M be a Γ -semiring and T a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M . Then every subset of T containing $T\Gamma M\Gamma T$ is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M .*

Proof: Let E be a subset of T such that $T\Gamma M\Gamma T \subseteq E$. Then

$$E\Gamma M\Gamma E \subseteq T\Gamma M\Gamma T \subseteq E.$$

Hence E is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M . ■

Theorem II.11. *Let M be a Γ -semiring. Then the following statements are equivalent.*

- (1) M is a GB-simple Γ -semiring.
- (2) $a\Gamma M\Gamma a = M$ for all $a \in M$.
- (3) $(a) = M$ for all $a \in M$.

Proof: (1) \Rightarrow (2) Assume that M is a GB-simple Γ -semiring and $a \in M$. By Lemma II.5, we have $a\Gamma M\Gamma a$ is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M . Since M is a GB-simple Γ -semiring, we have $a\Gamma M\Gamma a = M$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) Assume that $a\Gamma M\Gamma a = M$ for all $a \in M$ and let $a \in M$. Then, by (2), we have

$$(a) = \{a\} \cup a\Gamma M\Gamma a = \{a\} \cup M = M.$$

(3) \Rightarrow (1) Assume that $(a) = M$ for all $a \in M$, and let A be a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M and $a \in A$. Then $(a) \subseteq A$. By assumption, we have

$$M = (a) \subseteq A \subseteq M.$$

Thus $M = A$. Therefore M is a GB-simple Γ -semiring. ■

Lemma II.12. *Let B be a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of a Γ -semiring M and T a sub- Γ -semiring of M . If T is a GB-simple Γ -semiring such that $T \cap B \neq \emptyset$, then $T \subseteq B$.*

Proof: Assume that T is a GB-simple Γ -semiring such that $T \cap B \neq \emptyset$ and let $a \in T \cap B$. By Lemma II.3, we have $\{a\} \cup a\Gamma T\Gamma a$ is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of T . Since T is a GB-simple Γ -semiring, we have $\{a\} \cup a\Gamma T\Gamma a = T$. Thus

$$T = \{a\} \cup a\Gamma T\Gamma a \subseteq B \cup B\Gamma M\Gamma B \subseteq B \cup B \subseteq B.$$

Hence $T \subseteq B$. ■

Theorem II.13. *Let M be a Γ -semiring, B a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M and $\emptyset \neq A \subseteq M$. Then $B\Gamma A$ and $A\Gamma B$ are generalized bi- Γ -ideals of M .*

Proof: Since B is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M , we have

$$(B\Gamma A)\Gamma M\Gamma (B\Gamma A) = (B\Gamma (A\Gamma M)\Gamma B)\Gamma A \subseteq (B\Gamma M\Gamma B)\Gamma A \subseteq B\Gamma A$$

and

$$(A\Gamma B)\Gamma M\Gamma (A\Gamma B) = A\Gamma (B\Gamma (M\Gamma A)\Gamma B) \subseteq A\Gamma (B\Gamma M\Gamma B) \subseteq A\Gamma B.$$

Therefore $B\Gamma A$ and $A\Gamma B$ are generalized bi- Γ -ideals of M . ■

Theorem II.14. *Let M be a Γ -semiring and B a bi- Γ -ideal of M . Then B is a minimal generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M if and only if B is a GB-simple Γ -semiring.*

Proof: Assume that B is a minimal generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M . By assumption, B is a Γ -semiring. Let C be a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of B . Then

$$C\Gamma B\Gamma C \subseteq C \subseteq B. \quad (3)$$

Since B is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M and by Theorem II.13, we have $C\Gamma B\Gamma C$ is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M . Since B is a minimal generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M , we get $C\Gamma B\Gamma C = B$. Thus, by (3), we have $B = C$. Hence B is a GB-simple Γ -semiring.

Conversely, assume that B is a GB-simple Γ -semiring. Let C be a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M such that $C \subseteq B$. Then

$$C\Gamma B\Gamma C \subseteq C\Gamma M\Gamma C \subseteq C.$$

Thus C is a generalized bi- Γ -ideal of B . Since B is a GB-simple Γ -semiring, we have $B = C$. Hence B is a minimal generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M . ■

Theorem II.15. *Let M be a Γ -semiring having a proper generalized bi- Γ -ideal. Then every proper generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M is minimal if and only if the intersection of any two distinct proper generalized bi- Γ -ideals is empty.*

Proof: Assume that every proper generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M is minimal and let B_1 and B_2 be two distinct proper generalized bi- Γ -ideals of M . By assumption, we have B_1 and B_2 are minimal. We shall show that $B_1 \cap B_2 = \emptyset$. Suppose that $B_1 \cap B_2 \neq \emptyset$. By Lemma II.2, we have $B_1 \cap B_2$ is a proper generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M . Since $B_1 \cap B_2 \subseteq B_1$ and $B_1 \cap B_2 \subseteq B_2$, we get $B_1 \cap B_2 = B_1$ and $B_1 \cap B_2 = B_2$. Thus $B_1 = B_2$ which is a contradiction. Hence $B_1 \cap B_2 = \emptyset$.

Conversely, assume that the intersection of any two distinct proper generalized bi- Γ -ideals is empty. Let B be a proper generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M and C a generalized bi- Γ -ideals of M such that $C \subseteq B$. Suppose that $C \neq B$. Then C is a proper generalized bi- Γ -ideal of M . Since $C \subset B$ and by assumption, we have $C = C \cap B = \emptyset$ which is a contradiction. Therefore $C = B$, so B is minimal. ■

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